

CLASSICA

Validating AI in classifying cancer in real-time surgery

Midterm Recruitment Report (Study 1)

Document date: 29th June 2024

Document version: 2.2

Deliverable No: D4.2

Dissemination Level: Public

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 4.2 Midterm Recruitment Report (Study 1) outlines the recruitment status of Study 1 at the anticipated midterm recruitment point.

Work packages contributing to the outputs of this report are identified, and the role of this work in the context of the overall project is introduced. In particular, the factors that have affected recruitment to date are discussed, along with their potential impact for future recruitment. Additionally, ongoing plans to mitigate against any further delays are introduced.

The approach to recruitment to the study has been summarised into three phases: i) Planning, ii) Commencement, and iii) Expansion. Each of these phases is described in detail with reference to the relevant previously submitted deliverables.

The results section of this report details the relevant steps to the commencement of recruitment as they pertain to each clinical site, accounting for delays where applicable. The number of patients currently recruited at each site is presented, along with average monthly recruitment and projected recruitment going forward.

Finally, the impact of recruitment to date on the project's progress is explained, and future plans for maintaining and expanding recruitment are outlined.

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List of acronyms, definitions and abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BH	Beaumont Hospital
CTA	Clinical Trials Agreement
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
HPRA	Health Products Regulatory Authority
HUM	Humanitas Research Hospital
ICG	Indocyanine Green
JCA	Joint Controller Agreement
LEC	Local Ethical Committee
MDM	Multidisciplinary meeting
NIR	Near infrared
PIL	Patient Information Leaflet
WP	Work package

1 Introduction

Deliverable D4.2' Midterm Recruitment Report (Study 1)' describes the status of CLASSICA Study 1 at the targeted midpoint of recruitment. This deliverable takes account of how recruitment has progressed at the individual clinical sites, identifying challenges and successes. It highlights how these challenges have been overcome and what has been learned thus far. This will inform the recruitment of the remainder of the Study 1 period along with that of Studies 2 and 3.

The work described in this deliverable is dependent on the outcomes of previous work packages (WP) and deliverables, notably WP1' AI system refinement and support', WP2' Clinical Validation Preparation', and WP3' Training and Clinical Implementation', see Figure 1.

Figure 1. Workflow diagram illustrating the integration of work packages

It was initially intended that this deliverable be completed in month thirteen of the project. However, delays were experienced during Task 2.3 (Ethical Approvals) of WP2. Recruitment is dependent on securing ethical approval at each clinical site in order to allow for initiation of recruitment on schedule. These delays and their impact on recruitment are discussed further in the results section of this report.

Successful recruitment of patients to Study 1 is essential for the completion of the study and achieving the objectives set out at the beginning of the study. This deliverable poses an opportunity to assess what has been done well in the study up to this point in terms of maximising patient recruitment to achieve successful validation. It allows an opportunity to identify areas which may further improve recruitment throughout the remainder of Study 1 and also into Studies 2 and 3.

2 Approach

The work carried out can be broken down into three components, which are outlined below:

- i) Recruitment Planning
- ii) Recruitment Commencement
- iii) Recruitment Expansion

2.1 Recruitment planning

Recruitment planning commenced in WP2 with the drafting of the protocol along with the patient information leaflet (PIL) and consent form (D2.1). In particular the formalising of inclusion and exclusion criteria allowed for planning regarding the targeting of patients suitable for recruitment through multidisciplinary meetings, outpatient clinics and endoscopy lists.

Members of the multidisciplinary team at each clinical site (surgeons, research fellows, clinical nurse specialists) were familiarised with the inclusion criteria and pathway for recruitment at each individual site to ensure all patients suitable for inclusion in the project would be approached once the clinical phase of the project was commenced. These preparations occurred at each of the five clinical sites. Throughout this process, UCD played a supporting role, advising on appropriate recruitment pathways as had been used in the previous developmental study [1].

It has previously been demonstrated that staff familiarity with the aims of a study and its protocol is important in achieving target recruitment to studies involving the clinical environment [2]. To address this and support recruitment at the clinical sites, IRCAD produced a study instructional video (available to view online at 10.1111/codi.16769). This five-minute instructional video illustrates the processes that occur in theatre as part of the study. Given that the ICG NIR evaluation of rectal tumours may be new to some theatre staff, this video aids in improving understanding of the step-by-step processes involved.

Recruitment was dependent on the acquisition of ethical approval at each clinical site, the purchasing of equipment where applicable, the provision of insurance for each clinical site and the composing and signing of appropriate legal data agreements. UCD took the lead in providing the relevant documentation required for ethical approval at each site. This has been discussed in detail in deliverables D2.1 and D4.7. Clinical sites not previously in possession of a NIR camera liaised directly with Stryker, supported by UCD, to acquire the relevant camera for the study. UCD liaised with university-approved brokers to secure insurance for this phase of the project. This process was delayed by a number of months, contributing to a delay in the start of recruitment.

One clinical site, ZOL, has been subject to further delays in the preparation for recruitment at this site. This is due to a requirement by Belgian law for a Clinical Trials Agreement (CTA) to be in place for any observational study in order for ethical approval to be granted. As a formal CTA is not typical in Ireland for observational studies, an appropriate contract was required to be drawn up. The legal departments in both UCD and ZOL spent a number of months drafting a suitable CTA. This was finally agreed upon and signed on the 14th of December, 2023. This enabled ZOL to move forward with its application for ethical approval, which was granted in May 2024. ZOL are currently in negotiations with Stryker regarding the lease of equipment for the remainder of the project and will commence recruitment once this is in place.

2.2 Commencement of recruitment

Recruitment was commenced in each clinical site once all relevant ethical and legal requirements were in place. Suitable patients were identified through outpatient clinics, MDMs and endoscopy lists. Once it was deemed that a patient met the inclusion criteria as outlined in the protocol, they were approached by a suitably qualified member of the research team to discuss participation in the study. It has previously been demonstrated that the experience and expertise of staff members involved in

the recruitment process for clinical study may impact recruitment rates in such studies [3]. For this reason, and in order to comply with the requirements of each of the clinical sites, each team member involved in the recruitment of patients has a thorough knowledge of the study aims and protocol in addition to minimum research integrity requirements at the relevant clinical site. Once the patients were informed of the study aims and what would be involved in participation in the study, they were provided with the PIL, including relevant contact details and given time to review this. All patients were given an opportunity to ask any further questions regarding involvement in the study prior to signing the study consent form (D2.1). Recruited patients were issued with a CLASSICA study number, randomly generated by the CLASSICA-WEB platform. This was recorded on the consent form and in a coding key at each clinical site as per the Data Management Plan (DMP) (D2.4).

2.3 Recruitment expansion

Given the delays involved in the initiation of recruitment at the original clinical sites, additional clinical sites were recruited. The proposed additional clinical sites are outlined in **Error! Reference source not found.** below.

Each site was screened by UCD for its suitability as a clinical site. All new clinical sites must be represented by a Consultant Colorectal Surgeon with expertise in transanal minimally invasive surgery. Once deemed suitable for inclusion, a formal invitation to participate was made, and upon acceptance, study documents (protocol, CRF, PIL and consent form) were supplied. UCD assisted each new clinical site in its ethical applications. This process has been completed in BH, with recruitment commencing in March 2024. UHW and HUM have both made submissions to their respective ethical committees and are being supported in this by UCD. The remaining sites are in the process of reviewing the study documentation prior to making their ethical applications. HUM and UHW are already in possession of all relevant equipment for the study, with BH being supported in accessing the NIR camera. Relevant data agreements have been drafted for each of these sites in accordance with the DMP (see D2.4).

Table 1 Planned additional clinical sites

Full Name	Short Name	Site Lead	Status
Beaumont Hospital, Dublin, Ireland	BH	Prof. John Burke	Invitation to participate accepted. Currently recruiting.
University Hospital Waterford, Waterford, Ireland	UHW	Prof. Peter Neary	Invitation to participate accepted. Ethical approval underway.
Humanitas Research Hospital, Milan, Italy	HUM	Prof. Antonino Spinelli	Invitation to participate accepted. Ethical approval underway.
Oxford University Hospital, UK	OUH	Prof. Chris Cunningham	Invited to participate, initial ethical approval applications made. Participation ultimately not feasible.
Semmelweis University Hospital, Budapest, Hungary	-	Prof. Attila Zarand	Invited to participate, study documents supplied.

Full Name	Short Name	Site Lead	Status
St. Paul's Hospital, Vancouver, Canada	-	Prof. Carl J Brown	Initial invitation to participate accepted, study documents supplied.
Advent Health Cancer Institute, Orlando, Florida	-	Prof. Matthew Albert	Invited to participate.

In order to maximise patient recruitment at all clinical sites, IRCAD will develop a patient-focused study information video. This video will be available to the public via the project website (<https://classicaproject.eu>) and may be displayed in hospital waiting rooms or on the participating hospital websites. It will also be provided to patients as an adjunct to the PIL. The primary purpose of this video is to assist patients targeted for recruitment in their understanding of the study as part of the informed consent process. This is hoped to encourage high levels of patient participation. Additionally, increasing the profile of the study within the participating hospitals and the broader population will ultimately contribute to the communication and dissemination aims of our project.

3 Results

3.1 Recruitment targets

As discussed, WP2 challenges resulted in a delay in the initiation of recruitment at each of the clinical sites. There was approximately a six-month delay in the initiation of recruitment at most of the clinical sites. This has had an effect on recruitment targets at each of the affected clinical sites. However, it has highlighted a number of points in the study initiation process that are vulnerable to delays. This experience has made us better prepared for the inclusion of new additional clinical sites as the legal agreements required have already been drafted, existing insurance policies are already in place, and finalisation of these documents may be completed in parallel with submission to local ethics committees.

The current status of recruitment at each site is outlined in Table 2. To date, 76 patients have been recruited to the study in the four sites open to recruitment. While this is behind schedule with regard to the initial timeline set out for Study 1, average monthly recruitment suggests that the target recruitment for initial validation will be achieved in M35. With the inclusion of the additional clinical sites, as discussed earlier in this report, the study recruitment target will likely be reached earlier.

Each recruiting site is currently performing well on a monthly basis, with a mean of 1.85 patients per site per month being recruited (range 1.38-2.50). Each site is achieving a high recruitment rate among patients meeting inclusion criteria with a mean recruitment rate of 98% (range 95-100%). This high recruitment rate speaks to the quality of the PIL and consent process alongside the acceptability of the study's methodology to patients.

Table 2 Current recruitment numbers per clinical site

Site	Number of patients targeted for recruitment	Number of patients recruited	Recruitment success rate	Average Monthly Recruitment
UCD	20	19	95%	1.73
UNITO	-	-		-
BBGRAZ	17	17	100%	1.38
ZOL	-	-	-	-
VUMC	35	34	97%	1.79
BH	5	5	100%	2.5
<i>Total</i>		75	98%	7.40

3.2 Recruitment demographics

Recruited patient demographics fall in line with what would be expected of this patient population. Fifty-two males and 23 females have been recruited, with a mean age of 64.5. Twenty-five tumours were benign, 41 were malignant, with the remaining histology outcomes pending at the time of writing. Thirteen patients had neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy prior to their ICG assessment. A full description of the recruitment demographics per clinical site is summarised in Table 3.

Table 3 Current recruitment demographics

	UCD	VUMC	BBGRAZ	Beaumont	Total
Patients Enrolled	19	34	17	5	75
Male gender	12 (63%)	26 (76%)	11 (65%)	3 (66.7%)	52 (69%)
Mean Age (SD)	67.4 (11.2)	62.9 (11.6)	62.9 (11.5)	70.3 (24.5)	64.5 (12.1)
Carcinoma	8 (42%)	25 (73.5%)	8 (47.1%)	0	41 (54.7%)
Benign	7 (36.8%)	6 (17.6%)	9 (52.9%)	2 (40%)	24 (32%)
Pending	4 (21.1%)	3 (8.9%)	0	3 (60%)	10 (13.3%)
Neoadjuvant Rtx	2	7	4	0	13 (17.3%)

3.3 Video quality analysis

Of the 75 videos, 69 have been deemed of suitable quality for analysis. This high video utilisation rate speaks to the preparation and training that took place in the early phases of the project and the high performance of each of the clinical sites. The advances made in tracking and feature extraction algorithms (D1.2) have also contributed to this high video utilisation rate. Of videos deemed unsuitable quality for analysis, one case had reduced NIR intensity, and five were due to the fluorescence inflow phase not being recorded. In the early phases of the previous developmental study performed by UCD, surgeon camera movement, the presence of blood and bowel peristalsis were all identified as factors that could hinder video quality. Actions to minimise the impact of these issues for the CLASSICA were discussed at length during plenary meetings, on the monthly concalls, and formally incorporated into the protocol.

4 Impact & Conclusion

This deliverable describes the recruitment of patients to Study 1 of the CLASSICA project. Although initial delays were caused by the processes of obtaining ethical approval, insurance provision, and data agreements, no additional obstacles have been encountered at any of the actively recruiting centres.

Our current results will allow us to begin interim results analysis as part of WP5. As part of this interim analysis, UCD will assess the quality of existing videos, and feedback will be provided to individual sites as required in order to maintain the highest standard of data contribution throughout the project. Analysis can now be performed to compare the fluorescence intensity curve features between patients recruited to CLASSICA and those involved in the developmental study, which will determine the generalisability of the underlying physiological principles and mathematical hypotheses.

The experiences gained in this first early stage of the project will inform our recruitment of additional clinical centres and allow us to minimise delays with regard to securing ethical approval and other legal requirements at these sites. These foundations also support the preparation of documentation, ethical approval and regulatory approval required for Study 2. Most importantly, the progress in recruitment and initial analysis in Study 1 enables us to move forward with the initiation of Study 2.

5 References

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